

Action plan 2024–2027

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1. Adherence to the core commitments of CoARA

Satakunta University of Applied Sciences (hereafter SAMK) signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment on February 13th, 2023. We aim to ensure that the evaluation of research and researchers acknowledges diverse forms of research outputs, methodologies, and engagement, taking into account various career paths and individual circumstances while assessing the quality and impact of research. Full agreement can be accessed at: [CoARA agreement](#)

1.1 The Core Commitments of CoARA

By signing the CoARA Agreement, SAMK adheres to the following:

1. Recognise the **diversity** of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research.
2. Base research assessment primarily on **qualitative evaluation** for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
3. Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication-based **metrics**, in particular inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index.
4. Avoid the use of **rankings** of research organisations in research assessment.
5. Commit **resources** to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organizational changes committed to.
6. Review and **develop** research assessment criteria, tools and processes.
7. **Raise awareness** of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use.
8. **Exchange** practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition.
9. **Communicate** progress made on adherence to the Principles and implementation of the Commitments.
10. **Evaluate** practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research.

1.2 Universities of Applied Science – special characteristics of research

The main challenges that underlie the CoARA process stem from the academic research tradition. While for example, the inappropriate use of bibliometric indicators is a severe problem in some fields of science, its impact on the RDI functions in UASs is much less significant.

UAS-driven research and RDI work is distinguished by a strong focus on **development-oriented projects, applied research, and interdisciplinary collaboration**. As stated in the Finnish law, UASs have an important position in the **regional trade and industry, business, and well-being as well as competence ecosystems** guiding our efforts toward impactful outcomes. This orientation is evident in our assessment practices, recruitment procedures, and career development initiatives.

Although impact and diversity are embedded in many of our evaluation practices, it is important **to articulate the current practices and to further refine them**. This not only ensures **transparent and equitable evaluation processes** for our staff but also enables us to **share our best practices** with diverse research organizations and environments. In the long run, this approach has the potential to enhance the flexibility of researchers and experts moving between research, business, and well-being organizations.

UASs are relatively new players in the Finnish research landscape. The growth of UAS-driven research operations underscores the necessity for more systematic and transparent evaluation criteria. The CoARA process provides us an excellent opportunity to carefully **define our strengths and communicate them** to other research and RDI actors, authorities, and funders both nationally and internationally. Additionally, it provides a platform for refining our procedures.

1.3 Research at Satakunta University of Applied Sciences

SAMK is a multidisciplinary institution of higher education and an efficient actor in education, research, development, and innovation. In our operating area on the west coast of Finland, we are a significant creator of experts as well as a developer, a propeller of internationalization, and a promoter of entrepreneurship. The Finnish Education Evaluation Centre (**Karvi**) has audited SAMK. The **quality certification** is valid for six years as of March 16, 2022. SAMK also has an **ISO 9001:2015 compliant certificate**, granted by the DNV Business Assurance Management System Certificate.

The profile chosen in the new strategy is **People and Renewable Industry**. Satakunta is an industrial region that is clearly more important than its size for Finland's success and prosperity. The role of people in renewing industry is significant. SAMK's **focus areas** are Automation, Robotics and Artificial Intelligence, and Human Inclusion and Ability. **Emerging areas** are Security of Supply and Knowledge Management. SAMK collaborates with around

800 companies and communities every year. SAMK has **six research centers** to support companies and communities in developing their activities and identifying future business opportunities: RoboAI Research and Development Center, Business Intelligence Center BIC, Maritime Logistics Research Center, Research Center WANDER, Center for Tourism Business Development, and Research Center for Human Functioning.

SAMK is an active participant in the **European University Network**. SAMK has more than 100 international higher education partners. SAMK's research centers are part of the European higher education community and international research networks. SAMK strengthens the integration of international students, teachers, researchers, and experts into Satakunta and Finland together with companies and communities.

SAMK's **Entrepreneurship Accelerator** has produced more than 700 accelerator contracts and more than 400 knowledge-intensive enterprises. The entrepreneurship of the university's staff and students is seen as an asset for the university and for regional development. Transparent, equal, and consistent principles and practices of university-based innovation encourage entrepreneurship throughout the university community.

SAMK is committed to developing its research activities according to the national **Declaration for Open Science and Research**. The results of research activities that do not involve trade secrets or Intellectual Property Rights are distributed according to the principles of open science and research as widely as possible. Ethics is given the highest priority in SAMK's research. Research activities comply with ethical principles and relevant national, EU, and international legislation. Research follows the principles of the **Finnish National Board of Research Integrity (TENK)** to ensure voluntary participation, provision of information on the study, confidentiality, and data protection.

Our research volume is constantly growing. Hence, we also need to adapt our organization and operations to match the growing demands. In addition to the personal level challenges in researcher evaluation, we see the CoARA process as an excellent opportunity to review and further develop our organization-level research evaluation and reporting practices.

2 Objectives

In accordance with CoARA, SAMK aims to evaluate and update the assessment practices on three levels: 1) Research, 2) Researchers and experts, and 3) Research Organizations. During the CoARA implementation period, we will evaluate and update our assessment practices covering all three levels.

Research. We need to ensure that our assessment practices **include qualitative methods** (not based on metrics or counting papers/citations or similar numerical indicators) and encourage our employees to aim at impactful research that is of the highest possible quality. It remains crucial to proactively safeguard against the potential adoption of inappropriate quantitative assessment practices.

Researchers and Experts. We need to ensure that the merits of individual researchers and experts involved with in research are evaluated in a **transparent and fair process**. We will evaluate our current processes carefully and, if needed, implement novel evaluation strategies and tools that help us recognize an even larger variety of **research and research-associated merits**. While being a university of applied sciences, the **career paths** in our organization differ significantly from the traditional academic monorail type of career path. SAMK's researcher career path model has been in place for two years. We have **acknowledged researchers' contributions** to societal impact, business and university networks, regional ecosystems, project management, research funding applications, popular publications, and finally, also to research methodology that are particularly useful for universities of applied science. Our experience with the career path model has been very encouraging, and we will continue to improve and enhance its implementation.

Research Organizations. Finland is widely acknowledged for its leadership in promoting responsible research and assessing researchers, with extensive national collaboration overseen by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV). The CoARA agreement aligns with Finland's previously issued national recommendations, outlining a schedule for implementing reforms.

Additionally, SAMK undergoes regular evaluations conducted by authorities and research funding bodies, and our funding is directly impacted by the outcomes of these assessments. We look forward to the opportunities presented by CoARA to emphasize the **importance of applied research**. Furthermore, the CoARA agreement certainly increases our **visibility and attractiveness to new partners**.

3 Current situation and work packages of forthcoming actions

Commitment. SAMK has signed the CoARA agreement and is committed to evaluating and developing research and research assessment practices according to CoARA principles. Furthermore, SAMK follows the guidelines of the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity and the Declaration on Open Science and Research.

The current situation and the forthcoming actions with time schedules and responsible parties are presented in the following work packages.

WP 1. Research evaluation and forthcoming actions

Target 1.1. Research as a whole

Organizational-level external assessment has mainly been conducted by Karvi (Finnish Education Evaluation Centre) and the ISO 9001:2015 DNV partner. In addition, university and business partners, national and international funders, and other actors in SAMK's networks provide continuous feedback.

Actions in 2026 (Vice President for Research)

Peer review with the strategic university partners Centria and SeAMK.

Target 1.2. Research proposal evaluation

SAMK has the Project Manager's Manual, which is to support all staff in SAMK participating in projects, in particular, the Project Managers. The guidelines are valid, both in projects coordinated by SAMK and in projects that we partner. The manual consists of five main chapters and seventeen subchapters. The first chapter defines the project process, and how a project idea can enter to evaluation. The project initiator first has a discussion with a Head of Research, and where needed, with an RDI Coordinator. When the initiator wishes the idea to proceed to the evaluation phase, he/she prepares an A4 of the project idea by answering six questions.

Actions in 2025 (RDI Coordinators and Heads of Research)

The sparring process is streamlined, and the A4 evaluation criteria emphasizing the CoARA objectives are specified.

Target 1.3. Doctoral Accelerator evaluation

The Doctoral Accelerator is closely linked to the activities of SAMK Research Centers. The main goal is to enable doctoral students to link their research topics to SAMK's research projects for which external funding is sought, so that doctoral thesis and research work can be carried out as part of the implementation of the projects. SAMK associate professors can act as supervisors (first or second) of the dissertation, if all parties involved see the benefit

(university giving the degree, doctoral student, associate professor). The Accelerator increases the academic competence and social impact of SAMK staff, creates new and deepening business and university-university partnerships, and increases the practical impact of research.

Actions in 2024-2025 (Vice President for Research and Heads of Research)

Peer review with the West Coast Cooperation partner universities, Centria, TuAMK and VAMK. Furthermore, the Accelerator will support WP 2 actions.

Target 1.4. Research Centers

SAMK has six research centers to support companies and communities in developing their activities and identifying future business opportunities: RoboAI Research and Development Center, Business Intelligence Center BIC, Maritime Logistics Research Center, Research Center WANDER, Center for Tourism Business Development and Research Center for Human Functioning. SAMK has defined four criteria to launch a new center: it must be part of an ecosystem, its activities must be at the heart of the major business in the region, its activities are of high international quality, and it has a sufficient number of researchers and experts.

Actions in 2025-2027 (Research Management Group)

The research centers conduct self-assessment systematically once a year. The assessment is based on the current criteria, as well as from the perspective of CoARA criteria. External evaluation may be implemented at some point.

Target 1.5. Publications

Publications should be a "by-product" of normal research or teaching development, not the "main product". In other words, publications should not be produced solely for publication points, but have at least three more important objectives: to convey valuable information to our current and future partners, to communicate the expertise of both SAMK and the authors, and to increase visibility. Researchers have a strong track record of publishing in expert and professional journals, and publications with a social impact are well produced.

Actions in 2025-2026 (Vice President for Research and Heads of Research)

Manuscripts submitted to publication series, compilation publications of research centers, SAMK Journal, and online magazine are evaluated by internal and external reviewers. A wide variety of publications, both scholarly and more practical, are accepted for publication. In publication evaluation, COARA criteria are emphasized. However, there is a need to develop research quality skills and methodological skills and publish more in scientific arenas.

WP 2. Researcher evaluation and forthcoming actions

Target 2.1. Recruitment

The new recruitment process was established concurrently with the implementation of the career path model and the salary system for researchers. We see diversity as an asset. We value each researcher as an individual bringing together talents from diverse backgrounds and career stages around the world to build a successful future together. We believe in strong teamwork, openness, collaboration, and community.

Actions in 2026 (Vice President for Research and Recruitment Expert)

Peer review with the strategic university partners Centria and SeAMK.

Target 2.2. Researcher career path

The career path model for researchers includes positions as Researcher, Senior Researcher, Researching Senior Lecturer, Researcher Principal Lecturer, Chief Researcher and Head of Research. The criteria for fixed-term and permanent employment will be clarified. The prerequisites and duties for the positions are comprehensively defined. The new salary system for researchers was defined when the career path model was implemented.

Actions in 2024-2025 (Vice President for Research and HR Manager)

The career path model, the research positions and the salary system for researchers will be evaluated when the new SAMK strategy is officially launched.

Target 2.3. Rewarding

SAMK has several reward practices for all employees, such as performance pay and sports and cultural vouchers. At the Staff Day, Distinguished Workers of the Year are honoured. These include Success Story of the Year, Initiative, Teacher, Researcher, Publisher, and Communicator. No personal bonuses are currently in use.

Actions in 2026-2027 (University Management Group)

Discussion of current and future rewarding practices, including COARA criteria.
Peer review with the strategic university partners Centria and SeAMK.

WP 3. Analysis, participation and progress

Target 3.1. Analysis of the results in research assessments

All collected information will be analyzed and discussed to identify the major challenges in our processes. The key challenges will be selected for intervention. Experts from management, research centers, research support services and HR, together with researchers will be engaged in the process.

Actions in 2027 (Vice President for Research)

Tangible solutions to the selected main challenges will be implemented. The interventions can be small pilots or larger changes in the organization-level assessment policies. Each pilot is

evaluated, and decisions will be made on whether the novel process will become part of our internal routines.

Target 3.2. Analysis of the results in researcher assessments

As in 3.1.

Actions in 2027 (Vice President for Research)

As in 3.1.

Target 3.3. The internal, national, and international progress

SAMK follows the insights and guidelines of the Finnish National Chapter. Furthermore, SAMK follows the progress of the CoARA working group Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts. We will engage actively in discussions and advocate for topics that are particularly relevant to the UAS sector.

SAMK is an active member of the Finnish UAS network. Continuous discussions ensure timely and efficient implementation of CoARA principles on a national level. This network is a permanent collaboration platform that facilitates the implementation of progress in assessment.

Actions in 2024-2027 (Research Management Group and Communication Department)

The implementation of the CoARA action plan is overseen by SAMK's Research Management Group, with the Vice President for Research as the primary responsible party. The Research Managers' Team serves as the operational working group. A mid-term review and update of the Action Plan will be performed at the start of 2026 and the final evaluation at the end of 2027.

Internal communication actions ensure that our staff is informed about the process and comprehend the reasons behind the evolution of the evaluation framework, both within our institution and beyond. The process is showcased on SAMK's web page.

Schedule

		2024	2025	2026	2027
WP 1. Research evaluation and forthcoming actions					
T1.1.	Research as a whole - Peer review with the strategic university partners				
T1.2.	Research proposal evaluation - Sparring process is streamlined - A4 evaluation criteria with CoARA objectives are specified				
T1.3.	Doctoral Accelerator evaluation - Peer review with the West Coast Cooperation universities - Accelerator will support WP 2 actions				
T1.4.	Research Centers - Centers conduct self-assessment systematically once a year - External evaluation may be implemented at some point				
T1.5.	Publications - Manuscripts are evaluated by internal/external reviewers - COARA criteria are emphasized in evaluation - Need for research quality skills and methodological skills - Need to publish more in scientific arenas				
WP 2. Researcher evaluation and forthcoming actions					
T2.1.	Recruitment Peer review with the strategic university partners				
T2.2.	Researcher career path - Career path model, research positions and salary system for researchers will be evaluated based on new SAMK strategy - The criteria for fixed-term and permanent employment will be clarified.				
T2.3.	Rewarding - Discussion of current and future rewarding practices - Peer review with the strategic university partners				
WP 3. Analysis, participation and progress					
T3.1.	Analysis of the results in research assessments - Solutions to the main challenges will be implemented - Each pilot is evaluated, and decisions will be made on whether the novel process will become part of our routines				
T3.2.	Analysis of the results in researcher assessments - Solutions to the main challenges will be implemented - Each pilot is evaluated, and decisions will be made on whether the novel process will become part of our routines				
T3.3.	The internal, national, and international progress - A mid-term review and update of the Action Plan will be performed at the start of 2026 and the final evaluation at the end of 2027				